

Our little minions IV: small tools with major impact

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Conference

Little Minions

In our daily work, small self-made scripts (e.g. Python, R, Bash), home-grown small applications (e.g. GIS Plugins) and small hardware devices significantly help us to get work done. These little helpers – “little minions” [4] – often reduce our workload or optimise our workflows, although they are not often presented to the outside world and the research community. Instead, we generally focus on presenting the results of our research and silently use our small tools during our research, without even pointing to them, and especially not to the source code or building instructions.

This session will focus on these small helpers – “little minions” – and we invite researchers to share their tools, so that the scientific community may benefit and – perhaps – create spontaneously “special minion interest groups”.

As we have seen in last year’s “minion talks” since 2018 there is a wide range of tools to be shared. These may be perfect examples for your own minion creation. You can find an overview on <https://littleminions.link>.

At the virtual online conference CAA 2021 a lot of little minions of various research domains were published to the research community (see [1], pp. 53-55), e.g.:

- ▶ Democratization of Knowledge from Small Museums Online Digital Collections

Reusable Human and Machine-Readable Content Models by A. Avgousti, G. Papaioannou, N. Bakirtzis, and S. Hermon

- ▶ ChronochRt – make chronological charts with R by T. Rose, and G. G. M. Giroto
- ▶ re3dragon – REsearch REsource REgistry for DataDragons by F. Thiery, and A. W. Mees
- ▶ geoCore - A QGIS plugin to create graphical representations of drillings by M. Mennenga, and G. Bette
- ▶ Grading minion to the rescue by R. Visser
- ▶ Introducing a stature estimation tool for human skeletal material to the public by M. Koukli, V. Sevetlidis, F. Siegmund, C. Papageorgopoulou, and G. P. Pavlidis

Subjects

This session invites short presentations, lightning talks – aka “minion talks” (max. 10 minutes including very short discussion) – of small coding pieces, software or hardware solutions in any status of completion, not only focusing on field work or excavation technology, associated evaluation or methodical approaches in archaeology. Each “minion talk” should explain the innovative character and mode of operation of the digital tool. The only restriction is that the software, source code and/or building instructions are open and are or will be freely available. Proprietary products cannot be presented, but open and freely available tools designed for them. In order to support the subsequent use of the tools, the goal should be, that they are open available to the scientific community (e.g. GitHub, GitLab, etc).

Your Contribution

We invite speakers to submit a short abstract including an introduction into the tool, the link to the repository - if possible - to get access to the source code and an explanation which group of researchers could benefit from the little minion and how. The tools may address the following issues, but are not limited to: data processing tools and algorithms, measuring tools, digital documentation tools, GIS plugins,

hands-on digital inventions (for excavations) and data driven tools (e.g. Linked Data, CSV, Big Data). After previous years (pt. I CAA 2018 Tübingen, pt. II CAA 2019 Krakow, pt. III CAA 2021 Limassol/virtual) spontaneous success of “Stand-up-Science”, you will also have the opportunity to spontaneously participate and demonstrate what you have on your stick or laptop. If you want to participate without an abstract in the spontaneous section of the session, please send an email to us (even shortly before the conference). Please come and spontaneously introduce your little minion!

The minion session is designed for interested researchers of all domains who want to present their small minions with the focus on the technical domain and also for researchers who want to get ideas about what kinds of little minions are available to help in their own research questions. All of us use minions in our daily work, and often tools for the same task are built multiple times. This online session gives these tools that are considered too unimportant to be presented in the normal talks, but take important and extensive steps in our research, a home.

As an outcome of the session, we try to give support, that all presented tools and links to code repositories will be available for the research community in a “CAA little minion catalogue” [2] available for the public and extended in the future on a GitHub repository at [3].

References and Links

- ▶ (1) Cyprus University of Technology (2021). CAA 2021: Digital Crossroads. Book of Abstracts. URL: Book of Abstracts
- ▶ (2) <http://littleminions.link>
- ▶ (3) <https://github.com/caa-minions/minions>
- ▶ (4) F. Thiery, R. Visser and M. Mennenga (2021). Little Minions in Archaeology: An open space for RSE software and small scripts in digital archaeology. SORSE - International Series of Online Research Software Events (SORSE), virtual. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4575167